

FROM FILE VALIDATION TO STRUCTURAL MAPS, WE GOT YOUR PRE-INGEST COVERED

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Abstract – Tools and services that are both reliable and approachable to the end user benefit everyone in digital preservation. From validating digital objects to creating a submission information package, the goal is to enable a dependable and streamlined process. We at the National Digital Preservation Services in Finland have developed tools to help with this, two of which will be covered in this paper. The File Validation Service is a stand-alone online file validator that helps in catching errors in files as early as possible in the life cycle of digital content. The Pre-Ingest Library is a Python library that automates the creation of complex metadata documents needed for ingesting content into the services.

Submission Type – Short Paper

Keywords – file formats, submission information packages, tools, validation

Conference Topics – Haerenga – Journey

I. INTRODUCTION

The National Digital Preservation Services (DPS) in Finland [1] are centralized services that preserve Finnish digital cultural heritage and research data ingested by so-called partner organizations that manage and curate the data. All content ingested to the DPS must comply with strict requirements regarding both file formats and metadata, and the submission information package (SIP) must contain

a METS XML file which contains all metadata for the SIP. The digital objects must be valid and in supported file formats. The required metadata includes descriptive metadata as well as technical and provenance metadata in PREMIS format. The services employ a fully automated ingest process which validates all digital objects and requires machine readable metadata encapsulated in the METS document.

The partner organizations utilizing the DPS need services and tools to ensure the validity of digital objects as early as possible and to create SIPs complying with the requirements using automated workflows. We have created several tools and services that can be installed in the organizations' own backend systems for these purposes. They are meant to be used in the pre-ingest phase, in preparing and assessing digital content.

In this paper, we present our File Validation Service and the Pre-Ingest Library for pre-ingest actions. The online File Validation Service has a graphical user interface, but the file validation framework, run at the backend of the validation service, is provided publicly to install. These software components are developed by us in-house,

integrating several third-party tools. We provide our software as open source, free to use by anyone.

We have got very positive feedback about our software especially from our partner organizations, and many of them have integrated our tools in their own collection management systems. The partner organizations have been able to make their pre-ingest activities more efficient with our tools.

II. QUALITY ASSURANCE IN THE PRE-INGEST AND INGEST PHASES

The File Validation Service and the Pre-Ingest Library are used separately from the DPS ingest process, but we give some aspects about it to open up the context. The DPS employs a comprehensive validation process in the ingest phase when partner organizations send content to be preserved. The validation of the submitted content includes, for example, validation of metadata, file format validation, integrity checks, and virus checks. Since the validation is quite thorough and the amount of content sent to the DPS daily is high and varied, everything must be automated. We have built an ingest workflow that performs all validation steps without human intervention. The automation requires that the content metadata in the SIP must be fully machine readable. From this follows that the METS documents are complex and require a high level of expertise to create. Even a small and simple SIP may contain a substantial METS document.

The SIP structure and its contents are defined in the Metadata Requirements specification created jointly by the DPS and the partner organizations [2]. The SIP (tar or zip file) must contain the METS document, and a digital signature based on the METS document, in its root folder. All files in the SIP must be listed in the METS document. The METS document MUST contain descriptive metadata in a certain standard format, identifiers for the SIP and the service contract it belongs to, PREMIS metadata for each digital object of the SIP, provenance metadata as PREMIS events and agents, and a structural map.

The DPS and the partner organizations have in collaboration defined requirements that specify that the digital objects ingested to the service must be valid. File validity is checked with several tools in the ingest workflow. Digital object validation is performed for the following reasons:

- ensuring that the content is readable and usable,
- ensuring that the content is in the file format the metadata claims it to be and that it follows specifications,
- enabling future migration with known tools and processes,
- raising the technical quality, and
- documenting common errors in files.

We aid our partner organizations in SIP creation by providing tools (see Section IV). Invalid digital objects need to be fixed before ingesting them into the service. Our services support the organizations in investigating these errors and giving suggestions to solve them. However, the ingest process usually comes at a late stage of the life cycle of the content and the earlier any errors in the digital objects are caught, the easier it generally is to fix them. In several cases, the original creator of the data is already absent from the process when the content is ingested to the DPS. Fixing the content in these cases is cumbersome as it requires semantic knowledge about the content itself.

Tackling the issues of both creating complex metadata documents and handling invalid files rejected by the DPS ingest is not easy. With this in mind, we present our open-source, free and publicly available tools for file format validation and SIP creation.

III. FILE VALIDATION SERVICE

Sometimes the validity and well-formedness of a digital object is not readily apparent. We might be able to open the file with no problems, and everything looks fine on the surface, but validation tools are able to identify issues that are not visible to the human eye. Then again, a file may also be obviously broken and unusable, but we do not know why. In both cases, it is useful to rely on validation tools and software. The full ingest workflow with its automated validation process can be rather heavy, especially if we already know to expect a failure for a certain file, so a quick and easy way to check the validity of a file or two can be tremendously helpful.

The File Validation Service is an online service [3] that can be used for verifying the validity and support of a digital object in the DPS. It is built as a stand-alone service not integrated to the DPS ingest and access. The user uploads a file or a set of files to the service for validation using a web user interface.

After the uploaded file has been processed, the validation results are displayed in the user interface in a human-readable format. The end results are also downloadable as a machine-readable technical report.

While the service has been developed with our partner organizations in mind, it can be used as a general validation tool by anyone. However, the set of supported file formats corresponds to the specifications that are refined and agreed by the DPS and its partner organizations [4]. As such, the file validation service is not meant to identify and validate file formats not belonging to these specifications. Particularly exotic file formats will be neither identified nor validated.

The files are uploaded to the service using a secure transfer protocol via HTTPS. As soon as the upload is finished and all contents have been validated, the files are removed from the service. The web user interface consists of a simple web page, where the user may upload their files for validation. The uploaded contents are also scanned for viruses before any actual validation takes place.

After the upload has been completed and the virus scan has reported no threats, the workflow moves on to validation. The software used is File Scraper [5], also developed by the DPS. It is a framework of open-source third-party tools, meant for identifying file formats, gathering technical metadata, and checking the files' validity. This is the same tool that is used in the ingest workflow of the DPS, meaning that if a digital file passes the validation on the online service, it should also pass the validation when sent to preservation. When the validation workflow runs File Scraper, it first tries to identify the file format. Different detector tools are used for different file formats. Once the file format and MIME type have been identified, separate third-party and in-house scraper tools are used to collect technical characteristics and metadata about the file and perform checks to see if the file is valid. The technical metadata reported by the third-party tools is combined and normalized by File Scraper and written to a final validation report.

A summary of the validation results is displayed for the end user in the web user interface, and a more detailed technical report in JSONL format is available for direct downloading. In addition to the summary information displayed on the web page,

the report contains a wide range of technical characteristics that have been scraped from the validated files. Should the validation tools encounter errors, they will be listed in the technical report. The possible errors and error messages are gathered together with information about the third-party tool that reported them. This information is useful in identifying the reason for the rejection and planning a method for fixing the problematic file.

In addition to utilizing the online validation service, organizations have also implemented the underlying software, File Scraper, in their own processes and workflows for improving their pre-ingest activities.

IV. THE PRE-INGEST LIBRARY

The technological know-how required to create a fully machine-readable METS document containing descriptive, technical, structural, and provenance metadata is quite high. We have discussed this issue with our partner organizations, especially with organizations that might not have the resources to create a functioning pre-ingest workflow by themselves. To support organizations in ingesting content to our DPS and to advocate digital preservation on a national scale, we have developed a set of tools that aid in collecting metadata, validating files, and creating SIPs. These tools can be downloaded and used by anyone to create a machine-actionable SIP with a comprehensive METS document.

Our Pre-ingest Library [6] is a Python library for creating the SIPs and it has been built with integration into the backend systems of the partner organizations in mind. With only a few function calls, the user can create a valid METS document. In its simplest form, the user inputs a path to the content files and provides descriptive metadata in an XML format. The library is able to create all mandatory sections of the METS document using this basic information, including recursively processing all files in the given path.

The library collects the files into a SIP tar file together with the METS document and digitally signs the METS document. The result is a complete SIP that meets all the requirements of the DPS and which is ready to be sent to the repository for ingest.

More advanced use cases are also supported where the METS document is modified and

appended using Python functions. The Pre-Ingest Library integrates another Python library, METS Builder [7], to create the METS documents. The METS Builder functions on a lower form of abstraction, creating fully customizable metadata element by element into a METS document. It has functions and classes to build and compile different METS sections.

Files can be imported individually instead of importing a folder that is recursively processed. This is useful for providing digital object specific metadata such as individual identifiers. The files can also be individually linked to descriptive metadata sections and digital provenance metadata when imported individually. This allows a user to customize the created METS metadata to a high degree.

By default, the Pre-Ingest library creates a physical structural map, which follows the directory structure of the content. However, the functionalities of the METS Builder can be used directly to form more complex structural maps, e.g. importing one METS div section at a time. We also support the creation of logical structural maps for research data, based on user input that categorizes the content according to its function within a research dataset.

The Pre-Ingest Library creates automatic provenance metadata that documents the packaging process. Adding self-made provenance metadata is also possible. For example, a normalization event can be manually created to link two versions of the same digital object together in a case where an original non-supported file has been normalized to a supported file format. The digital object and agent links will be created both in the PREMIS metadata within the METS document, as well as linking the METS sections together in the file section or structural map of the METS document.

The Pre-Ingest Library also integrates File Scraper, the digital object identification and validation framework explained in Section III. Selected technical metadata can automatically be collected from files using the framework, and it is compiled to the METS document as PREMIS, MIX, audioMD or videoMD metadata. Adding custom technical metadata is also possible, which is useful for example for providing existing fixity information or own file format identification to the metadata.

V. FUTURE WORK

New file formats for detection, validation and metadata extraction will be added in File Scraper, depending how those are needed and how successful they are in our evaluation method. In the future, we will emphasize evaluating the preservability of discipline-specific file formats of research data.

The File Scraper tool will be linked to file format registries, and file validation error messages and possible solutions will be collected in a public database. This will bring more contextual information about the digital objects which will be integrated to the UI of the File Validation Service.

For the Pre-Ingest Library, the following step is to create a simple command-line library, as well as developing it further based on the feedback given by the partner organizations. For example, more complex structural maps based on user needs can be supported with functions that make their creation easier for the end user.

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to thank all members of the Digital Preservation team at CSC – IT Center for Science, as well as the national digital preservation collaboration group for their valuable comments and input for improving the National Digital Preservation Services. Especially, we thank the Ministry of Education and Culture of Finland for making this all possible.

